

Run	Attribute 1	Attribute 2	Attribute 3	Attribute 4	Attribute 5	Attribute 6
1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	2	3	2	2	2	2
3	1	2	1	2	3	1
4	2	1	2	1	1	2
5	1	3	1	1	2	1
6	2	2	2	2	3	2
7	2	3	1	2	3	2
8	1	1	2	1	1	1
9	2	2	1	1	2	2
10	1	3	2	2	3	1
11	2	1	1	2	1	2
12	1	2	2	1	2	1
13	1	3	1	2	3	2
14	2	1	2	1	1	1
15	2	2	1	2	2	2
16	1	3	2	1	3	1
17	2	1	1	2	1	2
18	1	2	2	1	2	1

Attributes	Definition	Levels
Controllability over adaptations Attribute 1	This factor considers how much control you, as the user, have over the way the app adapts to your needs.	Limited control over adaptations.
		Extensive control over adaptations.
Involvement of caregivers Attribute 2	This describes the role of caregivers in your daily use of the mHealth applications.	No access
		Limited access (e.g., updates or reminder only)
		Active involvement and jointly utilise the app
Usability of the app Attribute 3	This refers to how easy or intuitive the app is to use, even with the different adaptations.	Unpredictable and requiring users to learn it due to adaptations.
		Easy to use with a familiar interface.
Function usage patterns Attribute 4	This aspect reflects the app's adaptability based on how frequently you use different functions.	Several times a day
		Less than once a week
Frequency of adaptations Attribute 5	This shows how often the app's features change to match your preferences, which could range from occasional updates to more frequent adjustments	Adapt (only) once when user login
		Adapt monthly
		Adapt weekly
Granularity of adaptations	This highlights the scale of changes, whether they're broad	Adaptations are broad and impact the app significantly.

Attribute 6	adjustments affecting many parts of the app or small, targeted changes.	Adaptations are specific, affecting small aspects of the app.
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